

INTERACTIVE METHODS OF LEARNING ENGLISH THE IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract The article discusses the importance of the use of new pedagogical technologies in the teaching of English, and analyzes all the possibilities of the student, taking into account the complexity of mastering the subject. It also gives examples of new methods in language development and explains its importance.

Keywords: English, methodology, science, style, lesson, student, teacher.

Indeed, the task of teachers is to create a school lesson, a textbook that can meet the standards of internationally recognized countries through the development of a foreign language. Fortunately, the fact that English speakers can be found in the first grade of school shows that the system consumes a lot of the work of English speakers. In particular, the number of students reaching the international level in a foreign language is growing day by day. We are also delighted that in addition to our national universities, more than seven students per student are ranked in the top 1000 universities in the world. By the way, mastering science is a little difficult.

Mastering another language as a mother tongue depends on the skills of the teacher. The use of new teaching methods is important and effective. The level of assimilation of new technologies by students in a lesson is higher than in a traditional lesson. Below we will talk about the essence of such new pedagogical methods and their effectiveness in practice.

In many literature, the most popular interactive teaching methods today are Case Studio (or Study Cases), Blist Survey, Modeling, Creative Work, and Problem-Based Learning. According to the data obtained, interactive learning strategies include Brainstorming, Boomerang, Gallery, Zigzag, Zinamazina, Museum, Rotation, Round Snow. The approach to organizing group work in separating interactive teaching strategies from the structure of interactive teaching methods is in a sense based on comparing strategic approaches.

In fact, these strategies are also more applicable to interactive teaching methods, with no other distinction between them. Interactive Graphic Organizers: Fish Skeleton, BBB, Concept Table, Venn Diagram, T-Table, Insert, Cluster, Why, How? and others The distinction between interactive graphic organizers is based on the fact that the main ideas in such classes are expressed in writing in various graphic forms. In fact, working with these graphic organizers is more about interactive teaching methods. Below we will analyze some of the new interactive techniques.

This method is aimed at ensuring the activity of students in the classroom, encouraging them to think freely and freeing them from the inertia of the same thinking, providing a variety of ideas on a particular topic. Absolute prohibition of criticism of the opinion expressed by each participant encouraging any bites and jokes. The goal is for students to be able to freely participate in the learning process. The use of this method in the educational process depends on the pedagogical abilities of the teacher and the breadth of his thinking. When using the brainstorming method, the number of students should not exceed 10-15 people.

GENERAL IDEOLOGICAL METHOD OF ATTACK

The method helps create conditions for students to generate new ideas. When a group of 5 or 6 students completes various assignments or creative tasks that must be completed within 15 minutes, one of the group members will report this. The information provided by the group (task or solution of a creative problem) is discussed and evaluated by the teacher and other members of the group.

At the end of the lesson, the teacher announces the answers that are considered the best and most unique among the solutions to the given problem or creative problems. During the training, the performance of the group members will be assessed according to their level of participation.

6x6x6 METHOD The 6x6x6 method can be used to solve a specific problem or problem by simultaneously involving 36 students in a specific activity, as well as to determine the abilities of each group member and their views.

In this methodological exercise, 6 groups of 6 people each discuss the problem posed by the teacher. After the allotted time, the teacher reorganizes 6 groups. Each of the reorganized groups will have one representative from the previous 6 groups. The newly formed group members explain to their team members the findings presented by the group as a solution to the problem and discuss these solutions together. Advantages of the 6x6x6 method: - encourages each member of the group to be active; - ensures the expression of their personal views; - develops the ability to listen to the opinions of other group members; - be able to summarize a number of points put forward, as well as defend their point of view.

Most importantly, during each short session (20 minutes), the facilitator acts as a facilitator, listener, and speaker. This method can be used in several groups of 5, 6,

7 and 8 people. However, when using the 6x6x6 method between large groups, the time will have to be increased. Because it takes a lot of time to discuss and inform. Using the method in question, the group may cover one or more topics. Using the 6x6x6 method in the educational process requires the teacher to be active, pedagogical skills, as well as the ability to form groups in accordance with the goal.

Incorrect grouping can lead to incorrect assignments or tasks. When using this method, the lessons are organized in the following order:

1. Before the start of the lesson, the teacher places 6 chairs around 6 tables.
2. Students are divided by the teacher into 6 groups. When students are divided into groups, those who name each seat and receive name sheets will take their places.
3. After the students have settled in their places, the teacher announces the topic of the lesson and assigns specific tasks to the groups. A deadline will be set for discussion.
4. The teacher observes the activities of the groups, gives advice to the group members, where necessary, gives directions and asks the groups to make sure that the tasks set by the groups are solved correctly, asks them to complete the discussion.
5. At the end of the discussion, the teacher reorganizes the groups. Each of the reorganized groups will have one representative from the previous 6 groups. Members of the newly formed group explain to their team members the findings

presented by the group as a solution to the problem, and discuss these solutions together.

Pedagogical technology is essentially organized according to forms, methods and means, which increases the effectiveness of pedagogical activity and determines the interaction between teachers. In addition, it provides students with an in-depth knowledge of the subject. develops students' skills of independent, free and creative thinking. In addition, the necessary conditions will be created for students to realize their potential. He must also ensure the predominance of democratic and humanistic ideas in the pedagogical process.

REFERENCES

1. Jalolov Zhamol. Methodology for teaching foreign languages. Publishing house and printing house "Teacher", Tashkent - 2012.
2. Bekmuratova U.B. Essay "The use of innovative technologies in teaching English". Tashkent - 2012
3. Otaboeva, MR Using modern innovative technologies in teaching a foreign language and its effectiveness / MR Otaboeva. - Text: direct, electronic // Young scientist. - 2017. - No. 4.2 (138.2). - S. 36–37. - URL:
- 4.<https://moluch.ru/archive/138/39058/> (access data: 04/27/2020) Khatamova N.K., Mirzaeva M.N. "ENGLISH LESSONS
5. USED INTERACTIVE METHODS "(methodological manual), Navoi, 2006, 40 pages. 5. Kholdorova M., Fayzieva N., Riksittilaeva F." THE USE OF

ILM – FAN TA'LIMDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR, MUAMMOLAR, TAKLIF VA YECHIMLAR

ASSISTANTS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. " Tashkent: Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, 2005

6. Khoshimov O., Yakubov I. "METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE" (textbook) Tashkent: Publishing house "Shark", 2003.